

Addition of Sulphene to Substituted Benzalanilines

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1,4-Benzothiazines have been synthesized by the addition of sulphene, prepared *in situ* by the action of triethylamine on methane sulphonyl chloride, to 4-chlorobenzalanilines, 4-methoxybenzalanilines and 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines, through a novel rearrangement of the anticipated (2+2) cycloadducts.

In an earlier communication we reported the reaction of sulphene with benzalanilines¹. This paper describes the reaction of sulphene with C-phenylsubstituted benzalanilines e.g., 4-chlorobenzalanilines, 4-methoxybenzalanilines and 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines.

Addition of sulphene to substituted benzalanilines under the reaction conditions described earlier¹ either does not take place at all or results in poor yields. This is perhaps due to the poor solubility of these benzalanilines in solvent ether. This forced the authors to modify the reaction conditions.

Under modified conditions the reaction has been carried out by adding equimolar amounts of methane sulphonyl chloride and triethylamine simultaneously through dropping funnels to a constantly stirred benzene solution of the substituted benzalaniline, taken in a three necked flask, over 0.5 hr. Further stirring, filtration of triethylammonium chloride and removal of benzene *in vacuo* yields the crude product which is recrystallized from ethanol or methanol.

Moreover, it has also been observed that under the modified reaction conditions yields of the cycloadducts of sulphene and benzalanilines^{1,2} are increased.

4-Chlorobenzalanilines, 4-methoxybenzalanilines and 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines react with sulphene, generated *in situ* by the reaction of triethylamine on methane sulphonyl chloride to give 1,4-benzothiazines. These products are obtained through a novel rearrangement of the anticipated (2+2) cycloadducts (Scheme 1).

These products are identified and confirmed as 1,4-benzothiazines on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies. The infrared spectra of these products show sharp bands at about 3100 cm⁻¹ thereby indicating the presence of an associated NH group. The presence of this band suggests the

Scheme 1

migration of the sulphone group from the nitrogen atom of the aniline moiety to the *ortho*-carbon of the N-phenyl ring, followed by a protonic shift from the ring to the nitrogen atom under acidic conditions (Scheme 1), thus rearranging the four membered 2-thiazetidinium ring into a six membered 1,4-benzothiazine ring. Such migrations have already been reported in the case of sulphene adducts of nitrones³. The infrared spectra also show bands at 1300-1350 cm⁻¹ and 1140-1160 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of the sulphone group.

NMR spectral measurements also support the 1,4-benzothiazine structure assigned to these compounds. The nmr spectrum of the cycloadduct (IV) (R'=R''=OCH₃, R'''=Cl) shows one (NH) proton as a singlet at 7.2 τ , two methylene protons as a doublet at 2.8 τ , one (CH) proton at 6.6 τ and aromatic protons as a multiplet between 2.5 to 2.8 τ .

The adducts obtained by the addition of sulphene to 4-chlorobenzalanilines, 4-methoxybenzalanilines and 3,4-dimethoxybenzalanilines are recorded in Table 1.

Experimental

The following general procedure was adopted. A solution of 0.02 mole of 4-chlorobenzalaniline in

TABLE 1—1,4-BENZOTHAZINES

Sl. No.	Substituent in N-phenyl	Substituents in C-phenyl		Yield %	m.p.* °C
	R	R	R		
1.	H	H	Cl	75	140
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	Cl	72	124
3.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	H	Cl	70	120
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	Cl	70	109
5.	<i>p</i> -I	H	Cl	60	143
6.	H	H	OCH ₃	72	85
7.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	72	74
8.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	70	144
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	OCH ₃	75	195
10.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	H	OCH ₃	60	133
11.	H	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	70	99
12.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	70	105
13.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	68	197
14.	<i>p</i> -I	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	55	184

* All melting points are uncorrected.

The compounds gave consistent nitrogen and sulphur analysis.

150 ml of benzene was taken in a 500 ml three necked flask equipped with two dropping funnels. To the mechanically stirred solution, equivalent amounts

of methane sulphonyl chloride and triethylamine, each in 30 ml of benzene, were added simultaneously over a period of 0.5 hr. During the course of the reaction triethylammonium chloride precipitated out and an intense colour also developed. The reaction mixture was stirred for about 10 hr after the addition was complete. The triethylammonium chloride was filtered out. The filtrate was evaporated *in vacuo* yielding highly coloured semi-solid which was induced to crystallize by adding small amounts of ethanol. Cooling and filtration usually gave almost pure product. Recrystallization from ethanol gave pure adduct in 75% yield, m.p. 140°.

References

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